

IPBES AR BBA Chapter 2 – Snowballing literature search for literature on business dependency on biodiversity (R3)

Categories of the template for extracting data related to the magnitude, including the name of the category (category), its description (description) and the possible answer categories (answer categories).

Information category	Description	Answer categories
Id	Unique id given to each reference	-
Crop	Write the crop used in the paper that has an ISIC code. The list with ISIC subcategory	Select one of the crops listed in R4 (a total of 99 crops)
ISIC_cat	Name of the crop subcategory	Select one of the subcategories listed in R4 (a total of 99 subcategories)
Ecosystem_service	Ecosystem services studied	<p>Categories as in the typology of ecosystem services in the IPBES Global assessment report on biodiversity and ecosystem services (2019):</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Habitat creation and maintenance - Pollination and dispersal of seeds - Regulation of air quality - Regulation of climate - Regulation of ocean acidification - Regulation of freshwater quantity, location and timing - Regulation of freshwater and coastal water quality - Formation, protection and decontamination of soils - Regulation of hazards and extreme events - "Regulation of organisms detrimental to humans" - Energy - Food and feed

Information category	Description	Answer categories
		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Materials and assistance - Medicinal, biochemical and genetic resources - Learning and inspiration - Physical and psychological experiences Supporting identities - Maintenance of options - Other - Not specified - Multiple
Magnitude	Value of the magnitude measured	Open answer
Units	Units of the value of the magnitude	Open answer
Reviewer	Name of the reviewer that was a lead author (anonymized)	Open answer
Country	Country where the study was carried out	Open answer
Comment 1	Comments that could clarify the sense of the magnitude	Open answer
Comment 2	Name of the reviewer that was a contributing author (anonymized)	Open answer